

STRESS, LEARNING MOTIVATION, AND ACADEMIC BURNOUT AMONG STUDENT NURSES: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Stress, Learning Motivation, and Academic Burnout among Student Nurses: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

Attending nursing school is challenging. Students enrolled in a nursing program often complain of being academically burned out. As an educator, seeing, interacting with, and teaching learners suffering from burnout is tough. Nurse educators must be aware of this issue and act toward its resolution. Stress (Ma et al., 2022) and learning motivation (Mannerstrom et al., 2024) are variables associated with academic burnout. However, a gap exists in that current studies focused on assessing these factors from countries outside the Philippines and only in the context of public or private educational institutions but not on both. Therefore, this article aims to close the gap by elucidating how stress and motivation are connected with academic burnout in both public and private college nursing students. The inquiry was participated in by 719 nursing students from 4 private and state universities in the Philippines, utilizing modified standardized questionnaires and a 5-point Likert scale. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and linear regression were also employed as statistical tools. The results revealed that student nurses were experiencing high levels of stress ($M=3.89$, $SD=.977$), academic motivation ($M=4.25$, $SD=.798$), and academic burnout ($M=3.65$, $SD=1.10$), implying that nursing learners studying in universities suffered from burnout and academic stress but were highly motivated. In addition, it was found that academic burnout, stress, and external motivation are significantly related. Improving the quality of nursing education requires first identifying the causes of academic burnout among nursing students. Furthermore, policymakers, administrators, and educators can develop and implement regulations that advocate for healthier school life by understanding students' challenges.

Keywords: *academic stress, learning motivation, academic burnout, nursing students, correlation*

Introduction

Enrolling in nursing school is demanding. Students participating in a nursing degree frequently express feelings of fatigue, exhaustion, or, more severely, academic burnout. Academic burnout is physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion from persistent and intense academic stress. This frequently arises from a disparity between the requirements of academic tasks and the student's ability to manage those expectations. Student nurses frequently encounter stress in their academic pursuits due to substantial workloads from campus courses and clinical rotations, time limitations in completing and submitting demanding assignments, and admonishments from stringent clinical instructors with elevated academic expectations, among other factors. Observing, engaging with, and instructing students experiencing burnout is challenging. Nurse educators must recognize these contemporary concerns and take action to resolve them.

A recent study by Ma et al. (2022) found that 85.3% of nurses at a Chinese university suffered considerable to severe academic stress, while 36.1% reported emotional exhaustion. Aghajani Liasi et al. (2021) conducted a correlational study revealing that 16.3% of medical students experienced burnout, while 42.1% reported moderate to high-stress levels. Haile et al. (2019) reported that 34% of medical students in Ethiopia had academic burnout, with 79.9% suffering from academic stress due to dissatisfaction with classes and unengaging lectures. These data indicate that stress is a substantial predictor of academic burnout.

Even though student nurses are experiencing stress and may suffer from burnout, they may also have ways and means to cope with these adversities because they are equipped to understand stress and how to respond to it. Sometimes, a good mindset can battle the effects of stress, and this is where the concept of motivation comes into play. Academic motivation is the drive and desire that compels students to engage in and succeed at academic tasks. This factor influences academic burnout. Zalts et al. (2021), with a survey on medical students in Israel, Malaysia and China, stated that internal motivation negatively impacts academic burnout and that students motivated through external reasons have lower chances of getting burned out. In the Philippines, level 2 nursing learners in a private university in Central Luzon were experiencing high levels of academic stress. However, the students were also motivated to learn and succeed in their studies (Cabaluna et al., 2022).

However, a gap exists in that current studies focused on assessing these factors from countries outside the Philippines and only in the context of public or private educational institutions but not on both. Therefore, this article aims to close the gap by elucidating how stress and motivation are associated with academic burnout in both public and private college nursing students.

Research Questions

This study examined how stress and learning motivation correlate with academic burnout among student nurses. This report aims to address the subsequent research inquiries:

1. What is the level of academic stress among student nurses in terms of:
 - 1.1. fear of failure;

- 1.2. interpersonal difficulties with teachers;
- 1.3. personal inadequacy;
- 1.4. teachers' poor teaching methods; and
- 1.5. inadequate study facilities?
2. What is the level of academic motivation among student nurses in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation; and
 - 2.2. extrinsic motivation?
3. What is the level of academic burnout among student nurses?
4. Is there a significant relationship between academic burnout, and academic stress and academic motivation?

Methodology

Research Design

Research methods that were employed in the study include a descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive studies look at a population's characteristics, identify problems within a unit, an organization, or a population, or look at variations in characteristics or practices between institutions or countries (Siedlecki, 2020). Conversely, correlational design is a form of nonexperimental research that aids in predicting and explaining the relationships between variables (Seeram, 2019). By making use of the descriptive-correlational causal-comparative research design, the study will satisfy the objectives of the study.

Respondents

The study participants consisted of level 3 and 4 nursing students from various campuses of the College of Nursing. Level 3 and level 4 nursing students were chosen explicitly since they have already encountered the majority of experiences provided by nursing education in both classroom and clinical settings. Academic stress and burnout levels in junior and senior nursing students are significantly higher than in their early years (Valero-Chilleron et al., 2019).

The study participants were students with regular status, indicating their academic performance adhered precisely to the curriculum, with no documented instances of failing grades or unfinished or withdrawn courses. The irregular pupils and transferees were omitted from the investigation. Furthermore, the nursing students showed no mental or psychological inconsistencies, enabling their participation in the survey; involvement in the study requires a rational mindset and sufficient critical thinking skills. Students identified as psychologically unfit were excluded or recommended to withdraw from participation.

The study utilized a proportionate stratified random sampling method to get the participant count. The entire population was segmented into four categories based on the distinct university campuses participating in the study. The aggregate student population from the four universities was 1,446. The Raosoft sample size calculator determined a total sample size of 719. The precise figures for populations, samples, and participant percentages are delineated in the table below.

Table 1. *Distribution of Participants from Each University*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>Percentages (%)</i>
University A	549	227	31.6
University B	450	208	29.0
University C	236	147	20.4
University D	211	137	19.0
Total	1446	719	100

Instrument

This research employed three adapted and modified questionnaires to align with the study's objectives. The initial component of the survey instrument is the Academic Stress Scale, refined by Rajendran and Kaliappan (1990), initially comprising 40 items designed to evaluate academic stress. The investigator refined the statements to 25 and adjusted them to provide an accurate evaluation of the variable. The second section of the questionnaire comprises five subsections: fear of failure (7 items). Initially, 8, but 1 statement was excluded owing to insufficient reliability: interpersonal challenges with educators (9 items), personal inadequacies (8 items), ineffective teaching techniques employed by teachers (7 items), and inadequate study resources (9 things). This instrument was utilized in a recent study by Berdida (2023), which elucidated the correlation between academic stress and self-directed learning among nursing students.

The second part of the questionnaire is the Academic Motivation Scale by Vallerand et al. (1992), later adapted and improved by Ardenska et al. (2019), which was initially a 28-item questionnaire used to evaluate motivation to learn. The investigator has grouped similar statements and modified them to fit the study's objectives. This part of the survey tool is divided into intrinsic motivation (10 items) and extrinsic motivation (10 items). The reliability and validity of this survey tool were later assessed by Souza et al. (2021) among undergraduate nursing students. The analysis presented a model with three factors: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and demotivation. It was considered a reduced alternative to the original version of seven factors.

The final section of the questionnaire is the Academic Burnout Scale developed by Maslach (2018) and Maslach et al. (1997), which

consists of a 16-item survey designed to assess academic burnout. The investigator has reduced the statements to 10, as inquiries about diminished academic performance were omitted. After thoroughly examining the aforementioned concept, the researcher has developed and completed 20 statements to assess the phenomena, including the physical and physiological indicators of academic burnout. Maslach's Burnout Inventory/Scale has been extensively utilized in recent studies to assess the degree of academic burnout among nursing students (Chen et al., 2023; Ghods et al., 2023; Batista et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Lopes & Nihei, 2020; Sharififard et al., 2020; Valero-Chilleron et al., 2019).

The dissertation adviser assessed the survey instrument for content and face validity to confirm that the questionnaire items were pertinent to the study issues. Furthermore, three experts in nursing education, psychology, and research validated the questionnaire items to assess their relevance to the research issues. A reliability evaluation of the instrument was performed via a pilot test. Thirty level 2 student nurses responded to the questionnaire items. Additionally, the reliability of the survey items was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, yielding values exceeding 0.70, as detailed: fear of failure = 0.824, interpersonal difficulties with teachers = 0.849, personal inadequacy = 0.881, teachers' ineffective teaching methods = 0.846, insufficient study facilities = 0.821, intrinsic motivation = 0.943, extrinsic motivation = 0.848, and academic burnout = 0.956.

Procedure

The following procedures were applied to facilitate data gathering: First, the investigator asked permission to initiate research and obtained a letter of approval from the Deans of the College of Nursing of the respective study universities. The survey questionnaire and the consent letter were transcribed into Google Forms and distributed online via email. The investigator chose this survey distribution method because of the participant's unavailability due to non-uniformed schedules of classes and clinical duties. This approach also benefitted the participants because they could respond to the survey at their convenience and with no time constraints.

The letter of consent to the participants contained a detailed explanation of the terms and ethical considerations that serve as protection from data misuse and abuse. Moreover, the informed consent form was placed on a separate page before the questionnaire so the participants could withdraw their participation by not confirming with the designated page. Data collection began after the university confirmed its involvement in the study. After all participants responded, the investigator carefully compiled the replies and forwarded them to the university statistician for thorough data processing and analysis, guaranteeing optimal accuracy and dependability.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards. A survey instrument and participant consent letters were attached to the manuscript before it was sent to the Liceo Research Ethics Board (LREB). If the ethics board approved the study's procedures and techniques, it means they were done ethically.

The informed consent paper explains the study's goals and when volunteers might anticipate participating (October to November 2024). Participants were informed of the possible benefits and drawbacks, including privacy and security concerns. The investigator reassured the participants that following the safety protocols below would keep their data secure. The researcher emphasized that participants needed to be aware that their participation was completely voluntary and that they might stop or decline at any time, especially if they were sick or unable to finish the survey. The participants were guaranteed anonymity, and the information submitted to the investigator would be kept confidential.

In addition, the files with the participants' information and answers were saved on the investigator's computer, and the emails with these files were deleted as soon as the investigator received them. All data was open and honest, and the researcher indicated no bias or conflict of interest in the study. The participants received no incentives as they were informed that their participation was voluntary.

Results and Discussion

The tables below present, analyze, and interpret the data gathered, addressing the specific problems of the study.

Table 2. *Summary of Mean Scores for the Level of Academic Stress among Student Nurses*

<i>Academic Stress</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Fear of failure	4.28	0.83	Agree	High
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	3.85	0.979	Agree	High
Personal inadequacy	3.92	0.942	Agree	High
Teachers' poor teaching methods	3.84	0.994	Agree	High
Inadequate study facilities	3.57	1.14	Agree	High
Overall Mean	3.89	0.977	Agree	High

Scale: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree / Very High Academic Stress) | 3.51–4.50 (Agree / High Academic Stress) | 2.51–3.50 (Neutral / Moderately High Academic Stress) | 1.51–2.50 (Disagree / Low Academic Stress) | 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree / Very Low Academic Stress)

Table 2 displays the Summary of Mean Scores about the Level of Academic Stress among Student Nurses. The data indicates that students attained a mean score of $M=4.28$ ($SD=.830$) for Fear of Failure, followed by Personal Inadequacy ($M=3.92$, $SD=.942$), Interpersonal Difficulties with Teachers ($M=3.85$, $SD=.979$), Poor Teaching Methods by Teachers ($M=3.84$, $SD=.994$), and finally,

Inadequate Study Facilities ($M=3.57$, $SD=1.14$). The overall mean score is $M=3.89$, $SD=.977$, indicating a favourable assessment and elevated academic stress among student nurses. Meanwhile, the total mean standard deviation of $.977$ indicates that the data are more dispersed around the mean.

The statistics reveal that student nurses encountered considerable academic pressure from their apprehension of failing. The fear of failing an exam and, subsequently, a particular course is a significant source of stress for many students. The findings are corroborated by Alabduljabbar et al. (2022), who assert that fear of failure frequently correlates with negative behavioural consequences, including increased stress levels. Nursing students experience stress in academic contexts such as executing a return demonstration of a healthcare procedure, defending a case presentation, and particularly during quizzes or examinations, which compels them to persist in avoiding failure, as failure is deemed unacceptable in their pursuit of becoming healthcare professionals.

Disputes with professors or clinical instructors exacerbated considerable academic stress among nursing students. The study conducted by Wang and Xian (2024) substantiates the assertion that interpersonal conflicts between instructors and students substantially influence students' motivation, engagement, and psychological well-being in the classroom. Holding their educators in high regard, students make considerable effort to gain their favour. Students who achieve in their academic endeavours and impress their clinical instructors establish a constructive partnership.

Moreover, student nurses experienced considerable academic stress stemming from emotions of personal inadequacy. Personal inadequacy expressly stems from a failure to focus during study sessions. The findings have been verified by Ghods et al. (2023), who assert that personal insufficiency, sometimes manifested as inefficacy and self-doubt, substantially contributes to psychological problems, including elevated stress levels. The failure to exhibit competence in nursing and related medical courses considerably burdens pupils. Professionals in the health sector must possess the requisite knowledge and abilities to deliver satisfactory service to clients while minimizing or eliminating errors.

Aghajani Liasi et al. (2021) identified a correlation between personal inefficacy and diminished focus and concentration, adversely affecting learning and performance in medical students. The impression of personal inadequacy among student nurses arises from deficiencies in the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes expected of an exemplary nursing professional. The extensive study of health literature, the daily submission of numerous requirements, the execution of return demonstrations, oral defences, quizzes, and examinations, along with the necessity of maintaining acceptable interactions with classmates and clinical instructors, may present potential shortcomings for student nurses if they lack focus in performing these tasks.

The findings indicate that student nurses were subjected to significant academic stress due to their educators' or clinical instructors' ineffective teaching methods. Specifically, insufficient time allocated by teachers for submitting academic requirements reinforces the assertions of De la Fuente et al. (2021) that inadequate teaching methodologies induced stress during the COVID-19 epidemic. The study revealed that inflexible and unaccommodating teaching methods exacerbated students' academic stress, highlighting the need for teacher training in flexible and interactive instructional techniques. Most knowledge students acquire is derived from their lectures and clinical instructors, as nursing is a dynamic program characterized by the simultaneous interaction and collaborative goal attainment between students and educators. Consequently, ineffective teaching methods and styles may impede a learner's cognitive development. Student nurses find their instructors' inflexibility regarding evaluation techniques, work submissions, and management approaches difficult.

The results demonstrate that student nurses experienced considerable academic stress because of their institutions' inadequate study facilities and resources. There is a considerable shortage of classrooms allocated for group discussions, including case presentations and research activities. The assertions of Jagodics and Szabó (2023) correspond to these findings, as they expanded the demand-resource model to higher education, highlighting that insufficient study resources (e.g., inadequate access to technology, academic materials, and study environments) adversely affected students' engagement and mental health. Ample classrooms and study areas may facilitate student concentration by minimizing disturbances from adjacent courses. The results highlight the importance of aligning demands with enough resources to enhance student well-being (Jagodics et al., 2023).

Due to the high academic stress in student nurses, tailored interventions for high-risk groups, such as students in clinical or demanding academic programs, are essential for mitigating adverse outcomes (Hwang & Kim, 2022; Ma et al., 2022).

Table 3. Summary of Mean Scores for the Level of Academic Motivation among Student Nurses

Academic Motivation	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	4.17	0.785	Agree	High
Extrinsic Motivation	4.33	0.81	Agree	High
Overall Mean	4.25	0.798	Agree	High

Scale: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree / Very High Academic Stress) | 3.51–4.50 (Agree / High Academic Stress) | 2.51–3.50 (Neutral / Moderately High Academic Stress) | 1.51–2.50 (Disagree / Low Academic Stress) | 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree / Very Low Academic Stress)

Table 3 presents the Summary of Mean Scores for Academic Motivation among Student Nurses. As presented in the table, students obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.33$, $SD=.81$ for extrinsic motivation and a mean score of $M=4.17$, $SD=.785$ for intrinsic motivation. The overall mean score is $M=4.25$, $SD=.798$, which is described as agreeable and can be interpreted as high academic

motivation among student nurses. Meanwhile, the overall mean $SD=.798$ implies that the data are scattered around the mean.

The results indicate that student nurses are highly motivated to learn for internal reasons. Specifically, they go to college because of the pleasure they feel in expanding one’s knowledge by learning subjects that interest them. These findings are confirmed by the claims of Mannerström et al. (2024), who extended these findings to higher education, demonstrating that students with intrinsic motivations for attending university reported better identity formation, particularly in professional fields. Students enrolled in the nursing program have good internal motivation to become registered nurses following graduation. With this objective in mind, student nurses are eager to learn more about healthcare and enhance their existing knowledge to become ideal nurses in the future.

Furthermore, the results suggest that student nurses are highly motivated to learn due to external motives. Mainly, they go to college to secure a more prestigious job. These findings are supported by the statements of Zalts et al. (2021) that extrinsic motivators positively correlate with perceived academic rank and quality of life. The usual motivation for students to finish the nursing program is to become a registered nurse. However, the nursing market is overcrowded with thousands of professionals every half a year, particularly in the Philippines. This means the competition of getting a job in a prestigious medical institution is tough. That is why, for students, having competent marks and a beyond-adequate skill set is a must to be ahead of the competition.

Table 4. *Level of Academic Burnout among Student Nurses*

Variable	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Academic Burnout	3.65	1.10	Agree	High

Scale: 4.51–5.00 (Strongly Agree / Very High Academic Stress) | 3.51–4.50 (Agree / High Academic Stress) | 2.51–3.50 (Neutral / Moderately High Academic Stress) | 1.51–2.50 (Disagree / Low Academic Stress) | 1.00–1.50 (Strongly Disagree / Very Low Academic Stress)

Table 4 illustrates the extent of academic burnout among student nurses. The table indicates an overall mean score of $M=3.65$, $SD=1.10$, which is characterized as agreeable and interpreted as significant academic burnout among student nurses. Meanwhile, the total mean standard deviation of 1.10 indicates that the data are more dispersed around the mean. The findings indicate that student nurses were undergoing significant academic burnout due to excessive academic pressure and emotionally taxing circumstances.

The findings have been verified by Sharifard et al. (2020) and Aguayo et al. (2019), who assert that students encounter academic burnout when they experience emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and diminished feelings of personal achievement. It arises from persistent academic stress and is shaped by a complex interaction of individual, institutional, and contextual factors. Bauernhofer et al. (2019) observed that burnout symptoms are intensified by excessive workload and academic engagement. Student nurses often undertake academic tasks and clinical responsibilities due to a rigorous schedule. Persistent overwork and the failure to handle personal obligations lead to significant student burnout. This is also seen in medical students whose burnout symptoms peaked during graduation when the workload was excessive (Kilic et al., 2021; Shadid et al., 2020).

Research in China revealed that many nursing students suffered from emotional tiredness, a standard indicator of academic burnout. This occurred as a result of continual exposure to stressful circumstances and ineffective coping mechanisms (Ma et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021; Kong et al., 2021). A comparable scenario occurred in Spain, where numerous first to third-year nursing students experienced burnout, with symptoms intensifying as the academic year advanced (Valero-Chilleron et al., 2019). Additionally, five state colleges in Brazil indicated that 36.3% of their students exhibited significant burnout symptoms, notably emotional tiredness. This study reinforces the challenges encountered by student nurses in academically challenging circumstances, including excessive workload and emotionally taxing conditions.

Table 5. *Correlation Analysis between Students’ Academic Burnout, and Academic Stress, and Academic Motivation*

Variables	Academic Burnout			Remarks
	R-value	Effect Size	P-value	
Academic Stress	.541	Large	.000	Significant
Fear of failure	.434	Moderate	.000	Significant
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	.341	Moderate	.000	Significant
Personal inadequacy	.529	Large	.000	Significant
Teachers’ poor teaching methods	.378	Moderate	.000	Significant
Inadequate study facilities	.346	Moderate	.000	Significant
Academic Motivation	.067	Small	.074	Not Significant
Intrinsic motivation	.014	Small	.706	Not Significant
Extrinsic motivation	.114	Small	.002	Significant

Legend:
 Correlation Coefficient Range Effect Size/Strength of Relationship
 .50 and Above Strong/Large Correlation
 .30 to .49 Moderate Correlation
 .10 to .29 Weak/Small Correlation

Table 5 displays the Correlation Analysis among Students' Academic Burnout, Academic Stress, and Academic Motivation. The table illustrates that academic motivation ($p>.05$) and intrinsic motivation ($p>.05$) do not exhibit a significant correlation with students' academic burnout. Nonetheless, the Fear of Failure ($p<.05$, $r=.434$), Interpersonal Difficulties with Teachers ($p<.05$, $r=.341$), Teachers' Ineffective Teaching Methods ($p<.05$, $r=.378$), and Inadequate Study Facilities ($p<.05$, $r=.346$) exhibit a moderate positive significant

correlation with students' academic burnout; this indicates that a moderate increase in these variables will correspondingly elevate students' academic burnout. Extrinsic motivation ($p < .05$, $r = .114$) exhibits a modest positive significant correlation with students' academic burnout, indicating that a little increase in external motivation corresponds with an increase in academic burnout. Moreover, the variables Personal Inadequacy ($p < .05$, $r = .529$) and Academic Stress ($p < .05$, $r = .541$) exhibit a substantial positive correlation with students' academic burnout, indicating that a rise in these two variables will likely lead to an increase in students' academic burnout.

Yıldırım et al. (2023) assert that burnout is highly associated with fear of failure, with resilience and external motivation serving as mediators of this relationship, thereby substantiating these findings. Wang and Xian (2024) discovered that a positive teacher-student connection, facilitated by a supportive school climate, is inversely associated with student burnout. Haile et al. (2019) found that medical students' discontent with their instructors' pedagogical approaches intensified burnout, especially during clinical rotations. The absence of stimulating, student-centred activities and inadequate pedagogical approaches intensified emotional fatigue and depersonalization, resulting in burnout. Cornér et al. (2023) identified that inadequate frequency and quality of supervision and unequal access to research assistance exacerbated doctorate students' stress, fatigue, and cynicism.

Furthermore, Rahmatpour et al. (2019) established a substantial correlation between academic burnout and factors including field of study interest, GPA, and study habits. Students who exhibited disengagement from their discipline or showed subpar academic achievement were more prone to feelings of inadequacy and burnout. Finally, Allen et al. (2021) establish a positive correlation between stress and burnout among graduate students, such as weariness and cynicism, with sleep quality mitigating specific correlations. Similarly, Zalts et al. (2021) established that extrinsic motivators positively correlate with perceived academic standing and quality of life while adversely correlated with burnout.

Conclusions

The study illustrates that student nurses had significant academic stress due to elevated fear of failure, interpersonal challenges with instructors, feelings of personal inadequacy, ineffective teaching techniques, and insufficient study resources. The academic motivation of student nurses was enhanced by significant extrinsic motivation. Nonetheless, nursing students continued to experience significant academic burnout.

The investigation revealed a positive correlation between academic burnout and factors such as academic stress, fear of failure, interpersonal challenges with educators, feelings of personal inadequacy, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient study resources, and extrinsic motivation, indicating that student nurses experiencing academic stress while being externally motivated continued to endure academic burnout.

The following suggestions were put out in light of the study's findings and conclusions:

University policymakers may opt to establish frameworks that emphasize the importance of comprehending the factors contributing to academic stress, such as anxiety regarding failure, feelings of personal inadequacy, student-instructor relationships, and academic burnout. Effective counselling may stem from the identification of these elements. A policy may be implemented to prioritize the provision of adequate classrooms, study areas, facilities, equipment, and instructional resources for the College of Nursing, thereby alleviating undue stress and enhancing the educational experience for nursing students. Policymakers may thoroughly evaluate the effectiveness of their educators and clinical instructors, requiring suitable training or coaching in effective classroom management and pedagogical strategies. Initiatives that enhance academic motivation must be established, emphasizing advancement as the goal rather than exerting pressure on nursing students.

University administrators may offer staff training to identify early indicators of academic stress and burnout and coaching sessions to improve pedagogical practices and cultivate a positive relationship between educators and students. They may also allocate money to construct sufficient classrooms, study areas, and teaching facilities and provide the nursing department with adequate equipment and instructional aids to mitigate academic stress and enhance student nurses' class engagement. Furthermore, the administrators may augment their resources to ensure that mental health services, including counselling and motivation development programs, are available to all students. University administrators may establish a rigorous performance monitoring system for all lecturers and clinical instructors teaching nursing courses and collaborate with the College of Nursing to execute this.

The Colleges of Nursing may collaborate with the university to assess faculty effectiveness in teaching and classroom management, identifying areas for potential supplemental training. Furthermore, the colleges may provide coaching sessions on effective student management strategies. Such actions may cultivate an improved rapport between educators and their students. The nursing departments may urge their instructors to be vigilant in recognizing early indicators of academic stress and burnout and collaborate with the university's guidance and counselling department to address the mental health issues of student nurses.

Student nurses experiencing academic stress and burnout may receive comprehensive mental health support from the institution's guidance and counselling services, focusing on pragmatic coping skills. Departments may collaborate with the School of Nursing to assess and identify students facing mental health challenges. They may also aid in creating activities that enhance motivation to elevate pupils' positive external incentives.

Nursing educators may emphasize instructing their students on stress and academic burnout indicators while imparting ways for effective reduction and management. Lecturers and clinical instructors may engage in training and workshops focused on effective pedagogical practices while fostering a constructive academic relationship with students. The faculty may adopt a more adaptable strategy in managing their students, emphasizing cultivating student nurses' well-being to mitigate the detrimental impacts of stress and burnout, thereby enhancing their external motives to complete their nursing degree.

Student nurses encountering stress and academic burnout may pursue mental health therapy and fully utilize additional services provided by the universities' guidance and counselling departments. They may also engage with others who share similar experiences, allowing them to articulate their emotions to those who can genuinely empathize and exchange coping skills and stress management techniques. Nursing students may join motivation-enhancing initiatives organized by institutions to bolster their external motivation and augment classroom participation.

Finally, the shortcomings and approaches presented in this paper may serve as foundational stages for aspiring researchers to elevate their work. Future researchers may perform experimental studies to assess the efficacy of particular stress-reduction tactics, strategies, and practices on academic burnout. They may also investigate the long-term effects of academic motivation on nursing students' professional success and mental well-being.

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